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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

This data review examines the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP), a large cross-national survey project designed to support comparative research on social and political attitudes, values, and behavior. Launched in the 1980s, the ISSP is organized into thematic modules that enable both cross-national and longitudinal analysis across topics such as inequality, religion, national identity, and gender roles. Participation by post-Soviet and Baltic states has been relatively consistent overall, with particularly strong coverage of the Baltic countries and substantial inclusion of Russia, as well as Ukraine to some extent, across multiple modules. Finally, the review discusses key methodological features of the ISSP, including standardized questionnaires and nationally representative sampling, as well as practical aspects of data access. The data can be downloaded via the ISSP portal but require registration with GESIS, where the datasets are stored.

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Review of the International Social Survey Program (ISSP)

The International Social Survey Programme (ISSP) is a large cross-national survey project designed to support comparative research on social and political attitudes, values, and behavior. It was established in the early 1980s by research institutions in Germany, the United States, Great Britain, and Australia, and has since expanded to cover more than 40 countries.

The ISSP is organized around thematic modules, which are repeated at regular intervals (typically every five or more years). This structure makes it possible to combine cross-sectional comparisons with the analysis of long-term trends. To date, the ISSP has included the following core modules:

- Role of Government: 1985, 1990, 1996, 2006, 2016.
- Social Networks: 1986, 2001, 2017
- Social Inequality: 1987, 1992, 1999, 2009, 2019
- Family and Changing Gender Roles: 1988, 1994, 2002, 2012, 2022
- Work Orientations: 1989, 1997, 2005, 2015
- Religion: 1991, 1998, 2008, 2018
- Environment: 1993, 2000, 2010, 2020
- National Identity: 1995, 2003, 2013, 2023
- Citizenship: 2004, 2014
- Leisure Time and Sports: 2007
- Health and Health Care: 2011, 2021
- Additional modules are currently being developed (including Digital Societies.)

The following patterns of participation in the ISSP modules can be identified for the post-Soviet countries and Baltic states:

- Baltic states (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania): These countries are rather consistent participants, they appear in multiple modules, especially starting from the late 1990s. They are regularly covered in modules on Social Inequality (1999, 2009, 2019), National Identity (2003, 2013, 2023), Religion (2008, 2018), Environment (2000, 2010, 2020), and Family and Gender Roles (2002, 2012, 2022).
- Russia: Russia has been included in a relatively large number of ISSP modules, already since the early 1990s; these modules include Role of Government (1996, 2006, 2016), Religion (1998, 2008), Social Inequality (1999, 2009), National Identity (2003, 2013), and Environment (2000, 2010).
- Ukraine: Ukraine has been covered not very consistently but is present in several modules from the 2000s onward; these modules include Environment, National Identity, and Religion.
- Other post-Soviet countries (e.g., Georgia, Armenia): These countries appear only sporadically.

Currently, Estonia (SOGOLAS - Tallinn University), Georgia (Center for Social Sciences), Lithuania (KTU and VMU jointly), Russia (Levada Center) and Ukraine (Institute of Sociology of the National Academy of Sciences) are represented among the ISSP members.

Substantively, ISSP modules cover a wide range of topics of interest to social scientists and address pressing issues in many contemporary societies, including attitudes toward redistribution and inequality, gender roles, religious values and views on religion, environmental concerns, national identity, and attitudes toward work. Each module draws on standardized sets of questions, which allow for cross-national comparison. These are supplemented by a socio-demographic component covering variables such as age, gender, education, income, and occupation.

The target population in ISSP surveys is the adult population, usually aged 18 and older. Fieldwork is conducted by national research teams using nationally representative samples and probability sampling. Modes of data collection vary across countries and over time. ISSP surveys have traditionally relied mostly on face-to-face interviews, but telephone and online surveys have become more common in recent years.

Data collected through ISSP modules are publicly available and can be downloaded free of charge from the official ISSP [portal](#), though the links lead to datasets hosted by GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences (registration is required). Each module is distributed as a separate dataset, typically in SPSS and Stata formats, and sometimes also in R format, accompanied by detailed documentation, including information on the methodology of individual surveys. GESIS also provides a searchable [bibliography](#) of academic publications based on ISSP data.